

THEMATIC PRESENTATION AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING ORAL SPEECH AT A UNIVERSITY

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Abstract.

This article reveals the use of thematic presentations in the process of teaching a foreign language at a university. The technique for creating and effectively applying a multimedia thematic presentation is discussed.

Keywords.

thematic presentation, multimedia technologies

Introduction.

In connection with the development of information technology, the approach to organizing the process of teaching the German language in higher education has changed significantly. Visual aids made on the basis of multimedia technologies are widely used, making it possible to carry out the learning process at a qualitatively new level.

One of the most popular today are multimedia presentations. Performing a visual and illustrative function, multimedia presentations can be successfully used by a teacher at almost all stages of education: the introduction and consolidation of lexical and grammatical material, control of the studied material. In addition, the creation of projects in the form of presentations is an integral part of the student's independent work [24, 17].

Main part:

Presentations can be used as a time for listening, retelling texts, compiling dialogues. Such a wide range of applications of multimedia presentations is explained by the fact that presentations “bring diversity, enliven the learning process, increase the emotional impact on students, create a comfortable learning environment, and help form a model of real communication.” It is also important that the development of presentations increase the information culture of students, their motivation and self-esteem [3,288].

Experience shows that the so-called thematic presentations (presentations on the proposed topics) are an effective technique for improving monologue speech, which provides extensive material for communication in a foreign language.

With the help of the presentation, the student has the opportunity to build his speech logically and coherently, express their thoughts fully and correctly in linguistic terms. When organizing a lesson using a presentation, educational material presented clearly and accessible than if it were in the usual oral form. In the process of his speech, the student has the opportunity to use keywords, diagrams, tables, pictures that he has prepared [2,611]. This allows language learners to speak consistently, deployed, confidently and expressively. The use of thematic presentations is considered quite justified in the process of teaching both general and professionally oriented foreign languages. So, for example, for the students of mathematics direction, the topics „Berufliche Tätigkeit und Kommunikation“, „Geschichte der Mathematik“, „Geschichte der großen Mathematiker Usbekistans“ are suitable. These topics include voluminous material; moreover, when studying them, it is impossible to do without illustrative material. For these reasons, thematic presentations are the most successful teaching tool.

The use of multimedia performances in teaching The German language is a two-way process that contributes to the development of students' communicative competence. On the one hand, the student-speaker improves his speaking skills (monologue). On the other hand, the audience learns to perceive foreign speech by ear (listening skills), as well as to engage in a dialogue with the speaker on the topic of the presentation, thereby improving the skills of dialogical speech.

Creating a thematic presentation is not only an interesting, but also quite laborious process. To prepare a presentation, the teachers need to study a large amount of information in order to avoid templates and turn their work into a product of individual creativity. It should also be remembered about the structure of the presentation: an introduction, the main part with the development of the main provisions, logically related to each other, and a conclusion. The success of multimedia presentations largely depends on compliance with the requirements for creating a presentation: informative, concise, logical, structured, visual and literate [1, 152]. Compliance with these requirements is necessary to create a high-quality presentation, the use of which will make the lesson informative and effective.

Work on creating a presentation includes the following steps:

1. Selection and structuring of information on the topic.
2. Selection of illustrative material.

3. Drafting text and presentation design.
4. Preparation of a speech on the topic of the presentation.
5. Protection of the presentation, its discussion in class.

It should be noted that not only the individual creation of a presentation is effective, but also collective work, when, in addition to the advantages of using the presentation mentioned above, a sense of responsibility, teamwork.

As a rule, the creation of thematic presentations is of great interest to students, while, unlike the traditional retelling of the text, students of different levels of the German language proficiency are involved in the process, which undoubtedly optimizes the learning process.

Thematic presentations can be used effectively as an evaluation tool. Students are given the task of presenting a speech on an oral topic, accompanied by a multimedia presentation. Having studied the lexical and grammatical material on the proposed topic, they must independently compose oral messages, select illustrative material, and present their messages to the audience.

At the same time, in our opinion, the most successful is such a speech, when the presentation itself does not repeat the words of the speaker, but complements his speech, creating a complete and vivid picture of the speech [3,289].

The practice of using presentations in the process of teaching the German language in non-linguistic specialties of Uzbekistan universities revealed some typical mistakes made by students:

1. The text of the presentation is not structured, there is no logical connection between the blocks of the presentation.
2. Too much text on one slide, small font used.
3. Unsuccessfully selected slide background.
4. Presentation slides are designed in different styles.
5. Unsuccessful selection of illustrative material (inconsistency with the theme of the presentation, excess or lack of illustrations).

A serious disadvantage is that senior students do not like to use graphics, diagrams, and diagrams as illustrative material, when necessary, because they do not know the constructions and speech clichés used to describe digital information. Meanwhile, these elements of the presentation can be used in the professional field of future specialists, so the teacher needs to pay special attention to this [35 25].

The abundance of lexical, grammatical and stylistic errors in the presentation is often due to the fact that the presentation material was originally created by

translating the Uzbek language text into the German one, which is unacceptable, since students must learn to use the German language sources.

The quality of the thematic presentation is evaluated by the teacher according to the following criteria:

- Compliance of the content of the presentation with the stated topic;
- Structured presentation text;
- Visual design of the presentation;
- Literacy of presentation;
- Performance.

Conclusion.

Therefore, the conducted analysis allows us to conclude that it is expedient to use thematic presentations in the German language classes, with the help of which it becomes possible to realize the communicative function of the language. The ability to speak to an audience in the German language using a multimedia presentation in the future will allow students to become professionally sought-after specialists.

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